

SOUTH BELLMORE VETERINARY GROUP REVIEW: MAKING SURE OF THE BEST HEALTH FOR YOUR PETS

For many years, South Bellmore Veterinary Group has been known as a veterinary group that only provides the finest and the most trusted pet care service in Long Island New York. Its high-quality service is evident on its advanced equipment and machinery along with the extensive experience of each member of its staff. You can easily find its hospital clinic since it is located on Merrick Road in Bellmore, Long Island New York, and it is not far from Wantagh, Merrick, Freeport, and Seaford.

The group also has good relationship and connection with well-known experts that help them provide the best result to every category of their full service. The group continues to strive to give the service each animal deserves. With their unending dedication and hard work, it is not surprising that clients from Long Island, Queens, and Brooklyn continue to seek their pet care service.

Below explains each service that is being offered by [**South Bellmore Veterinary Group**](#):

Boarding

The group will definitely provide the best comfort and safety to animals through their boarding service. But be reminded that new visitors need to pass the group's pre-boarding examination to guarantee the safety and health of both the pets of new clients and their neighbors in the clinic. Because of this, you need to make sure first that your pets were on flea and tick preventative and were current with their vaccinations.

Dentistry

Your pets will surely receive the best dental care with South Bellmore Veterinary Group's dentistry service. The group has one of the best equipment used for this service. In particular, you can find quality ultrasonic scaler and polisher, along with a high-speed drill on their dental machine. Because of such equipment and a digital dental x-ray unit, the group is confident to conduct regular cleanings, dental exams, surgical extractions, root-planing, and gingival resection on your pets. Your pets will certainly receive anesthesia and will be properly monitored during dental procedures and of course during in-depth surgical procedures too.

Dermatology

The group also promises a good pet skin care to your pets. With their in-house lab, expect them to quickly diagnose and treat the dermatologic problems of animals such as bacterial and

fungal disease, ectoparasites like demodectic and scabetic mange, ear problems, and allergy testing/shots. And to completely put pet owners at ease, the group offers good shampoos, ointments, and flea and tick control products as well.

Ophthalmology

You don't need to worry about the eye care needs of your pets because the group can take care of them. In unfortunate cases where pets have glaucoma, conjunctivitis or uveitis, you can count on South Bellmore Veterinary Group on treating such problems. Its specialists will make sure of successful ophthalmologic surgery, which may include entropion/ectropion surgery, cherry-eye repair, conjuncival flaps, and enucleations. The group is also capable of correcting congenital eyelid malformations in particular breeds. As previously mentioned, renowned experts have been providing guidance to the group in assuring positive results to every service, and on this case, its cataract surgery and advanced ophthalmology cases are under the supervision of a seasoned expert on this regard.

Internal Medicine

In order to diagnose and treat the medical problems of your pets fast, the group has been using in-house blood analyzers, which is very helpful in giving accurate findings. Look forward to a trustworthy service that is backed by board-certified internists together with prominent specialists on veterinary ultrasound and internal medicine.

General and orthopedic surgery

You will never find negative descriptions on its surgical suite and the skills of their veterinary surgeons that are equipped with many years of extensive experience. The group can assure you positive results on their surgeries even if it is a complicated case. Disappointment is not in their vocabulary so don't be surprised for their good job on abdominal and thoracic surgery, eye surgery, perianal surgery, total ear canal ablations, and orthopedic procedures.

Radiology and cardiology

South Bellmore Veterinary Group offers a lot of services to give convenience to pet owners in taking care of their beloved animals, so it's no surprise to find radiology and cardiology included on its list of services offered. Equipment used by the staff is guaranteed to give the best results such as their x-ray machine, ultrasound machine, and EKG. This particular service is under the careful assistance of certified radiologists and cardiologists.